

Prominence and Discoverability of European Works in SVOD Catalogues: A Methodological Protocol for an Eye-Tracking Study with Film Audiences

Introduction

The Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD) obliges European Union Member States to promote European works across both linear broadcasting and on-demand audiovisual media services (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2018). In the context of streaming platforms, this obligation includes not only ensuring a certain share of European titles in catalogues, but also guaranteeing their prominence, that is, making them sufficiently visible and findable for audiences in practice. National regulators have implemented this requirement through a variety of measures, ranging from detailed, binding obligations to more general recommendations, often combining prominence tools with financial support schemes and other forms of regulation.

Existing policy documents highlight several concrete mechanisms through which prominence may be operationalised in subscription video-on-demand (SVOD) environments. These include indicating the country of origin in catalogues, providing search functionalities specifically targeting European programmes, placing promotional materials for European works on home pages, highlighting recent European titles, and using trailers or pop-up visuals to draw attention to them ([Promotion of European works in practice | Shaping Europe's digital future](#)). At the same time, the AVMSD framework deliberately leaves room for flexible implementation, allowing SVOD providers to choose the tools they deem most effective, while regulators monitor and evaluate whether the overall goal of promoting European works is achieved. This flexibility is considered important in a rapidly evolving market, but it also raises questions about how prominence is enacted at the level of user interfaces and everyday audience practices.

Against this regulatory backdrop, the European SVOD market is today heavily dominated by two global platforms, Netflix and Amazon Prime Video. Netflix has emerged as the largest SVOD provider in Europe, with the EMEA region representing the platform's biggest and fastest-growing subscriber segment. Amazon Prime Video is the second-largest SVOD service in Europe, holding a substantial market share overall and even outperforming Netflix in some national markets, such as Germany. Together, these platforms shape a large part of how European audiences access film and television content online, and they therefore constitute a critical arena for examining whether European works, including those from small national industries, are effectively given prominence in practice.

Recent research on European film policy and screen media has extensively discussed quotas, support schemes and circulation patterns of European works, including in the context of small European film markets and their structural disadvantages in terms of availability and export capacity (Nielsen et al., 2024; Damásio et al., 2025). At the same time, CresCine's audience-focused studies have begun to analyse how viewers in small markets encounter

domestic and European titles on streaming platforms, with particular attention to content diversity, catalogue composition and emerging viewing patterns (Grácio et al., 2025; CresCine WP7, 2025). However, there is still limited empirical evidence on how prominence requirements inspired by the AVMSD are translated into concrete interface features and user journeys on global streaming platforms, and existing work does not yet provide micro-level analyses of gaze, attention and search paths that would show how prominence (or its absence) is experienced in the moment of interaction with SVOD catalogues. This work addresses this gap by proposing a methodological protocol for an exploratory eye-tracking study of film audiences navigating SVOD catalogues in two European countries. Developed within the CresCine project (Work Package 7.2), the protocol combines laboratory-based eye-tracking experiments with retrospective think-aloud interviews to investigate how users search for European works on Netflix and Amazon Prime Video, and how catalogue structures, metadata and promotional elements shape their behaviour. The focus on small and medium-sized European film ecosystems further situates the study in ongoing debates on cultural diversity, exposure and the position of smaller production countries in global streaming markets. This focus is particularly important because, for smaller European industries, the challenge is not limited to production or circulation, but also concerns the conditions of digital visibility within transnational platform environments. Even when European works are formally present in catalogues, they may remain peripheral in navigational pathways if they are weakly labelled, poorly contextualised or absent from the promotional logic of the interface. The protocol proposed here therefore treats discoverability not simply as a technical issue, but as a cultural and industrial problem linked to platform power, market asymmetries and the mediated exposure of smaller national cinemas.

The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. How do users visually and behaviourally interact with SVOD catalogues when they are tasked with searching for European films and series?
2. To what extent do catalogue metadata, filtering options and home-page promotions support or hinder the prominence and discoverability of European works, particularly from small European film markets?
3. What kinds of obstacles and workarounds, including the use of external search engines, emerge in audience attempts to locate European content under realistic time constraints?

By articulating these questions and detailing the associated methodological design, the protocol aims to contribute both to the empirical understanding of audience experiences of European works on global platforms and to broader policy discussions on how AVMSD prominence obligations play out in practice within SVOD catalogues.

Research design and case selection

This study adopts an exploratory, laboratory-based design that combines eye-tracking and qualitative retrospective interviews to examine how users navigate SVOD catalogues when searching for European works. The focus is on two major platforms, Netflix and Amazon Prime Video, which together dominate the European SVOD landscape and thus play a central role in the implementation of AVMSD prominence obligations in practice. Netflix was selected as the

largest SVOD provider in Europe, with the EMEA region constituting its biggest and fastest-growing subscriber segment, while Amazon Prime Video was included as the second-largest service, holding a 24% market share and leading in some national markets such as Germany.

Platforms

Netflix was selected as the primary case study because it is the largest subscription video-on-demand (SVOD) service in Europe and CresCine ecosystem (Nielsen et al., 2024). Since its European launch in 2012, Netflix has rapidly expanded its subscriber base and now constitutes the most widely used streaming platform in several European countries, with the United Kingdom, Germany and France among its key markets. Recent industry data indicate that the EMEA region is Netflix's largest and fastest-growing subscriber segment, accounting for around one-third of global subscriptions and adding more than 12 million new subscribers in 2023 alone, with net growth more than double that of the UCAN region (United States and Canada) (FableData, 2023). Additional cataloguing tools such as the unofficial Netflix Online Global Search (uNoGS) further underline the platform's extensive territorial reach and help document catalogue availability across countries.

Amazon Prime Video was included as a second case because it represents the other major SVOD player in Europe. Market estimates for 2023 suggest that Prime Video holds roughly 24% of the European SVOD market, making it the second-largest service after Netflix, and even leading the market in Germany with a 34% share compared to Netflix's 27%. The platform also maintains significant positions in other large territories such as the United Kingdom and France and combines global catalogues with locally tailored offerings, thereby exerting substantial influence over what European audiences can access online. Taken together, Netflix and Amazon Prime Video form a de facto duopoly in many European markets, which justifies focusing on these two services when investigating the visibility, promotion and discoverability of European works on SVOD platforms.

Within this broader landscape, the present study is situated in Poland and Portugal, both of which belong to the CresCine ecosystem of small and medium-sized European film industries. These two countries provide access to distinct national catalogues of Netflix and Amazon Prime Video, shaped by geoblocking and territory-specific licensing arrangements, and thus offer a pertinent context for examining how the availability and prominence of European works vary across local SVOD environments. Given its exploratory scope and limited sample size, the study does not aim at statistical generalisation to all European audiences; instead, it seeks to generate fine-grained insights into user interaction patterns and discovery processes under realistic catalogue conditions in two contrasting film market settings.

Sampling strategy: three screening approaches

Before designing the experimental tasks, a three-step screening of film availability was conducted to assess the feasibility of using CresCine-related titles in the eye-tracking study. When examining the availability of CRESCINE titles in SVOD catalogues in 2023, we expected to find selected samples of films, however this availability is restricted to selected territory and subscribers plan.

Table 1. Number of CresCINE features available on global SVoD platforms

Source: [Performance Indicators - Distribution — CRESCINE https://www.crescine.eu/small-film-industries/distribution#6](https://www.crescine.eu/small-film-industries/distribution#6)

Approach 1. Films case studies under task 7.5

First, a subset of titles originating from CresCine's Work Package 7.5 sample was checked in the Polish and Portuguese catalogues of Netflix and Amazon Prime Video. This list included:

- Kneecap (Ireland, 2024),
- On Falling/Aurora (Portugal, 2024),
- Os Demónios do Meu Avô (Portugal, 2022),
- Girl with the Needle (Poland/Sweden/Denmark).

Manual verification performed between 21 and 23 March 2025 showed that none of these titles were available in the two platforms' catalogues for the tested territories.

Table 2. Films from 7.5 in Netflix and Amazon Prime Polish and Portuguese catalogues (discoverability by original, English and Polish title)

Title	Netflix PL	Netflix PT	Amazon PL	Amazon PT
KNEECAP (2024) IE	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
On Falling (2024) PT	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
The demons of my grandfather (2022) PT	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
Girl with the needle (2024) PL, SK, DK	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
Safe Place (2022) IT	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
A lucky man (2022) DK	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable

Source: Own study, checked manually in online catalogue between 21-23 March 2025.

An analysis of four representative titles demonstrated that none were accessible on either Netflix or Amazon Prime during the verification period.

Approach 2. Top 50 titles best performing internationally films in 2022-2020 from CRESCINE’s ecosystem

Second, the research team examined the availability of the Top 50 best-performing films from the CresCine ecosystem in terms of international admissions for the years 2020–2022, based on data provided by the project.

Table 3. Top 50 internationally best-performing films (2020–2022) from the CresCine ecosystem

Top 50 titles: international admissions									
Original title	Prod. year	Prod. country	Director(s)	Film Make	FIC/DOC	Genre (IMDb)	Total International / domestic admissions	Nb. markets	
Vesper	2022	LT, FR, BE	Kristina Buozyte, Bruno Samper	Live-Action	Fiction	Adventure, Drama, Sci-Fi		13	
Holy Spider	2022	DE, DK, FR, SE, JO, IT	Ali Abbasi	Live-Action	Fiction	Crime, Drama, Thriller		19	
Close	2022	BE, FR, NL	Lukas Dhont	Live-Action	Fiction	Drama		17	
The Cellar	2022	IE, BE, US	Brendan Muldowney	Live-Action	Fiction	Horror, Mystery		7	
Tæmet Ninja 2	2021	DK, US	Thorbjørn Christoffersen, Anders Matthesen	Animation	Fiction	Animation, Comedy, Family		9	
Flugt (documentary)	2021	DK, SE, NO, FR, US, ES, IT, GB	Jonas Poher Rasmussen	Animation	Documentary	Animation, Documentary, Drama		31	
Wild Mountain Thyme	2020	IE, GB	John Patrick Shanley	Live-Action	Fiction	Comedy, Drama, Romance		13	
Fatima	2020	PT, US	Marco Pontecorvo	Live-Action	Fiction	Drama, War		17	
Retfærdighedens ryttere	2020	DK	Anders Thomas Jensen	Live-Action	Fiction	Comedy		34	
Wolfwalkers	2020	IE, GB, LU, FR	Tomm Moore, Ross Stewart	Animation	Fiction	Adventure, Family, Fantasy		12	
Drømmebyggerne	2020	DK	Kim Hagen Jensen, Tonni Zinck	Animation	Fiction	Adventure, Comedy, Drama, Family, Fantasy		36	
Bigfoot Family	2020	BE, FR	Jeremy Degruson, Ben Stassen	Animation	Fiction	Family		37	

Source: Nielsen, J. I., Bengesser, C. H., Øfsti, M., & Kostovska, I. (Eds.) (2024, May 14). Small European Film Markets: Portraits and Comparisons. <https://www.crescine.eu/small-film-industries> (excerpt)

Cross-checking these titles against the Polish and Portuguese catalogues again revealed a very limited presence of such films, with most entries unavailable on both platforms and only occasional exceptions accessible in specific non-tested territories or via expiring licensing windows on Amazon Prime.

Table 4. Best performing internationally films from CRESCINE ecosystem from 2022 to 2020 in Netflix and Amazon Prime Polish and Portuguese catalogues (discoverability by original, English and Polish title)

Title (year, countries of production)	Netflix PL	Netflix PT	Amazon PL	Amazon PT
Vesper (2022, LT/FR/BE) ¹	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
Holy Spider (2022, DE/DK/FR/SE/JO/IT) ²	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
Close (2022, BE/FR/NL) ³	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
The Cellar (2022, IE/BE/US)	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
Ternet Ninja 2 (2021, DK/US)	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
Flugt / Flee (2021, DK/SE/NO/FR/US/ES/IT/GB)	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
Wild Mountain Thyme (2020, IE/GB)	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
Fatima (2020, PT/US) ⁴	unavailable	unavailable	available	unavailable
Retfærdighedens ryttere / Riders of Justice (2020, DK) ⁵	unavailable	unavailable	available ⁵	unavailable
WolfWalkers (2020, IE/GB/LU/FR)	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
Drømmebyggerne (2020, DK)	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
Bigfoot Family (2020, BE/FR) ⁶	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable
Druk / Another Round (2020, DK/SE/NL)	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable	unavailable

Source: Own study, checked manually between 21-23 March 2025

Approach 3. Discoverability by country of origin

Third, in order to generate a workable set of European films for task design, the researchers undertook a broader keyword-based search by country of origin. Using combinations such as “Danish film” or “Portuguese film” within the platforms’ catalogues, and restricting attention to titles released in roughly the past ten years, they compiled a list of European films from

¹ Available on Netflix only in Thailand (uNoGS: <https://unogs.com/movie/81565954/vesper>).

² Available on Netflix only in Argentina, Brazil, Colombia and the United States (uNoGS: <https://unogs.com/movie/81659282/holy-spider>)

³ Available on Netflix only in Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Mexico and Thailand (uNoGS: <https://unogs.com/movie/81616693/close>).

⁴ Available on Amazon Prime Video in Poland at the time of checking, with limited time window (leaves the service within 9 days)

⁵ Available on Amazon Prime Video in Poland: https://www.primevideo.com/detail/00739J5N4OYG1X1XAQ77HJ8B8D/ref=atv_dp_share_cu_r

⁶ Available on Netflix in Australia, Canada, the United Kingdom and the United States (uNoGS: <https://unogs.com/movie/81315367/bigfoot-family>).

CresCine-relevant countries that were actually available in the Polish and Portuguese catalogues. The outcome of this screening is summarised in the table 5, which presents a sample of CresCine-ecosystem film productions available in the Polish catalogues of Netflix and Amazon Prime Video.

Table 5. Discoverability by country of origin in Polish catalogue of Netflix and Amazon Prime

#	Title (year)	Country of production	Availability in Poland
1	Against the Ice (2022)	Iceland, Denmark	available on Netflix
2	The Siege of Jadotville (2016) ⁷	Ireland, South Africa	available on Netflix
3	Bytte bytte barn / Maybe Baby (2023) ⁸	Denmark	available on Netflix
4	Undskyld jeg forstyrrer (2012) ⁹	Denmark	available on Netflix
5	Fatima (2020) ¹⁰	Portugal, United States	available on Amazon Prime Video (time-limited, 23/03/2025)
6	Riders of Justice / Retfærdighedens ryttere (2020) ¹¹	Denmark	available on Amazon Prime Video

Source: Own study, checked manually between 21-23 March 2025

This procedure resulted in a **small but usable pool of titles**, with a relative concentration of Danish productions and a more modest representation of other small European markets.

The selected sample is subject to several important limitations that constrain the scope and generalisability of the study. First, the low discoverability and availability of films from the CresCine ecosystems in the analysed SVOD catalogues made it impossible to design comparable eye-tracking tasks for each national ecosystem; within roughly the last ten years, Danish productions were disproportionately represented, while other small markets yielded very few accessible titles. Second, platform design features and data practices restrict the extent to which “clean” browsing conditions can be created: Netflix does not offer an incognito catalogue

⁷ <https://www.netflix.com/pl/title/80041653>

⁸ <https://www.netflix.com/pl/title/81664637>

⁹ <https://www3.stage.netflix.com/pl/title/80094960>

¹⁰ https://www.primevideo.com/detail/0U67B121TXLQ10I7FA9QLOHMG1/ref=atv_dp_share_cu_r

¹¹ <https://www.primevideo.com/detail/0O739J5N4OYG>

view, so the study had to rely on repeatedly creating and deleting new user profiles within paid accounts, and clearing cookies, which can mitigate but not fully eliminate personalisation effects. Third, geoblocking and territory-specific licensing mean that the experiment is limited to the local conditions of the Polish and Portuguese catalogues; even with the use of VPNs, the location is tied to the country of the registered account, preventing a systematic extension of the protocol to other Member States within the same experimental framework.

Participants and recruitment

The eye-tracking experiment was conducted with a convenience sample of 24 adult participants, drawn from Poland and Portugal, with approximately 8–12 participants per country. All participants were native speakers of the local language (Polish or Portuguese) and were required to be at least 18 years old at the time of participation. Recruitment proceeded via snowball sampling, primarily involving students and acquaintances of students, reflecting the exploratory and non-representative nature of the study.

No strict exclusion criteria were applied with respect to educational background or prior SVOD use, although participants needed to have normal or corrected-to-normal vision. Some participants had existing experience with streaming platforms, but for the purposes of the experiment all interactions took place within new sub-profiles created under the researchers' paid Netflix and Amazon Prime accounts, thereby minimising the influence of previous viewing histories and personalisation. Participants provided informed consent before the start of the experiment and were informed that they could withdraw at any time without negative consequences. The study is embedded within the CresCine project and is conducted in line with project and institutional ethical standards.

Materials and apparatus

The experiment was carried out in controlled laboratory settings in Poland and Portugal. In each location, participants were seated at a desk facing a computer monitor equipped with a remote eye-tracking device mounted just below the screen. The eye-tracker, a Tobii system (T-series/X3-series), recorded binocular gaze data at a resolution sufficient for interface-level analyses, with an accuracy of approximately ± 0.5 degrees of visual angle, corresponding to roughly 0.5 cm on the screen at a viewing distance of about 50 cm. Such accuracy is generally regarded as adequate for studies of web-based usability and interaction patterns.

Eye-movement data were captured and processed using iMotions software, which enabled the definition of Areas of Interest (AOIs) across the SVOD interface (e.g. search bar, genre menus, recommendation rows, metadata panels) and the extraction of fixation-based metrics. Participants interacted with the Polish or Portuguese web versions of Netflix and Amazon Prime Video via a standard web browser, using fresh sub-profiles that were created and deleted as needed, with cookies cleared between sessions to reduce residual personalisation effects. The researcher's workstation, located behind a divider in the same room, allowed the experimenter to monitor the eye-tracking signal and task progression while remaining out of the participant's direct field of view.

Procedure and task design

Each experimental session followed the same general procedure. After providing informed consent and completing a short demographic and media-use questionnaire, participants underwent a standard eye-tracker calibration procedure to ensure accurate gaze recording. They were then introduced to the general purpose of the study—to explore how users search for films on streaming platforms—without emphasising European works explicitly at the outset, in order to avoid priming effects.

Participants performed a series of tasks on Netflix and Amazon Prime Video, presented in a fixed or counterbalanced order depending on the final implementation in each lab. Tasks were designed to simulate realistic but time-bounded use scenarios and to probe key aspects of AVMSD prominence requirements. All task instructions were provided both orally and on paper; the printed instructions remained available throughout the session so that participants could revisit them if needed. The main task types were as follows:

1. **Free exploration task.** Participants were asked to explore the platform’s home page and catalogue to familiarise themselves with the layout, navigation options and available content, while being asked about their general familiarity with SVOD catalogues.
2. **European works and country-of-origin tasks.** Participants were instructed to find films that fulfil certain criteria related to European origin, such as “a European film” or “a film produced in a specific small European country”, and to identify how the country of origin and other relevant metadata were displayed. These tasks targeted the visibility of origin information, the availability of filters or categories related to European content, and the presence (or absence) of dedicated European sections.
3. **Prominence and promotion tasks.** Participants were asked to identify any elements of the interface that seemed to highlight European works—for example, curated rows, home-page banners, trailers or pop-up windows featuring European titles, especially recent works. The aim was to observe whether and how prominence measures prescribed or encouraged by AVMSD were implemented at the interface level.
4. **Accessibility and versions tasks.** In some tasks, participants were asked to check which language versions, subtitles or accessibility features (e.g. audio description) were available for a given European title. This component connected discoverability with broader questions of access and inclusion.
5. **Selection task.** Finally, participants were invited to select a film they would like to watch, based on their interaction with the catalogue and recommendations, thereby revealing how interface design and promotional structures influenced their choices.

The time allowed for each task was deliberately limited, typically ranging from 30 seconds to one minute, in order to mimic the pressure users experience when searching for content in everyday settings. If participants found a task too difficult or frustrating, they were allowed to abandon it; such drop-out decisions were recorded as part of the behavioural data.

Measures and data analysis

The protocol specifies a multi-layered measurement strategy that combines eye-tracking metrics, behavioural indicators and qualitative accounts. On the quantitative side, key eye-tracking measures include Time to First Fixation (TFFF) on predefined AOIs (e.g. search bar, “European film” rows, country-of-origin fields), total fixation duration within each AOI, number of fixations, and scanpath characteristics, including regressions between AOIs. These measures are intended to capture how quickly and intensively participants attend to interface elements that may facilitate or hinder the discovery of European works.

Behavioural data include task completion times, number of clicks required to reach target information, success or failure in completing tasks, task abandonment, and the use of external search engines (e.g. resorting to Google when unable to find a film within the catalogue). Such indicators provide evidence on the efficiency and perceived usability of the platforms' search and navigation tools with respect to European content.

To address the limitations of gaze data alone, each session is complemented by a Retrospective Think-Aloud (RTA) interview conducted immediately after the eye-tracking tasks. During the RTA, participants are invited to comment on their decisions, difficulties and emotional responses while viewing selected screen recordings or describing key moments from memory. The interviews focus in particular on points of confusion, reasons for abandoning searches, perceptions of recommendation rows and promotions, and justifications for turning to external search engines. Audio-recorded RTAs will be transcribed and analysed using qualitative content analysis, aiming to identify recurrent patterns of perceived obstacles and strategies across participants and platforms.

Given the exploratory nature of the study and the small sample size, the analysis will be primarily descriptive and comparative rather than hypothesis-testing. Eye-tracking and behavioural metrics will be summarised using descriptive statistics and visualisations (e.g. heatmaps, gaze plots, click-path diagrams), with particular attention to differences between tasks, platforms and national catalogues. Qualitative findings from the RTAs will be integrated to enrich and contextualise the quantitative results, providing a nuanced picture of how prominence and discoverability of European works are experienced in practice on Netflix and Amazon Prime Video.

In analytical terms, discoverability is understood here as a process rather than a single observable event. It emerges through the interaction between interface cues, search strategies, metadata interpretation, time pressure and the user's prior assumptions about where European content is likely to be located. This process-oriented perspective makes it possible to examine not only whether participants eventually find a title, but also how effortful, indirect or fragile that discovery path is across different platform environments.

Methodological conclusions

The design of this web-based catalogue eye-tracking study follows established methodological recommendations in human-computer interaction and usability research and is explicitly built around data triangulation. Bojko (2009) stresses that heatmaps and fixation-based visualisations must be grounded in carefully defined Areas of Interest (AOIs) and robust data-collection procedures to ensure reliable and interpretable results, an approach adopted here through systematic AOI definition and calibration. In line with Siirtola and Rähä (2009), the analysis strategy reduces the voluminous eye-tracking output to a set of core indicators—fixation heatmaps, time spent within AOIs and transitions between AOIs—allowing for structured comparison of user attention across interface elements. At the same time, we recognise that eye-tracking alone can only show where users look, not whether they are engaged, frustrated or confused, especially in environments where catalogue design and pop-up windows may divert attention from active search towards more passive scrolling. For this reason, gaze measures are complemented in this protocol by quantitative behavioural data (such as task-completion times, number of clicks and task abandonment) and by qualitative retrospective think-aloud (RTA) interviews, inspired by Gerjets et al. (2011) and subsequent methodological work (Materska-Samek, 2020), which elicit participants' own accounts of their strategies, obstacles and interpretations. Together, these converging forms of evidence—gaze patterns, interaction metrics and verbal reflections—enable a triangulated assessment of how

users experience and negotiate SVOD catalogues, strengthening both the validity and explanatory power of the study's findings.

More broadly, the proposed protocol contributes to the methodological discussion on how cultural policy objectives can be studied at the level of interface interaction. By bringing together regulatory concerns, platform analysis and audience-oriented eyetracking, the study offers a way of examining how policy ideals such as prominence are translated—or fail to be translated—into concrete user experiences. In this sense, the protocol is intended not only as a technical research design, but also as a framework for connecting audiovisual policy with the lived realities of digital navigation.

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